

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Wandera****FIRST NAME: Mike****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references
The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)
The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 2016 on Windows 10

The seven key concepts with the page number in the text

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-8)
3. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
4. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
5. Chicago Manual of Styles (EUCLID 2019, 49-55)
6. Capitalization (EUCLID 2019, 45-46)
7. Quotations Marks (EUCLID 2019, 6-7)

PROFESSIONAL ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I worked with the private sector for some years, after which I joined the government. Whereas English is not my mother tongue, I have encountered the language from my elementary school days as an official means of instruction. My use of the English language has continued during my work engagements and even outside work during a conversation with other people since it is the official language of my country Uganda. After reading the coursepack materials provided by EUCLID for ACA-401 period one (1) and watching the online video provided, I realized the package would help me improve my English understanding to enable me to write better professionally acceptable work. The need to use facts to support evidence in essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 3) is key to my future career.

Furthermore, the coursepack outlined the various ways of plagiarism that I did not understand before. Henceforth, I will reference the source of information cited in my academic and professional work. The knowledge and skills gained will help me write assignments, theses, and dissertation and use it in my daily work. The learning of some of the recommended software applications like Grammarly and Zotero was challenging in the beginning. However, I have learned their essential use with persistence, and I appreciate the value they provide to write professional error-free work.

2) **EVIDENCE-BASED ESSAY**

There is no official definition of the word *essay* as presented by chapter one of the ACA-401 period one (1) coursepack. Whereas there is no official definition of the word *essay*, according to Wikipedia, “the word essay derives from the French infinitive *essayer*, to try or to attempt.” Wikipedia provides one of the definitions as a “prose composition with a focused subject of discussion” or a “long, systematic discourse.” Wikipedia further affirms that essays have become key to formal education and necessary for free-range response questions in countries like the United States and the United Kingdom. I agree with the Wikipedia assertion, which states that in “[academic] an essay is used to judge the mastery and comprehension of the material [for students],” which has to be “done logically and factually.” It is vital to communicate with other people based on facts derived from evidence (EUCLID 2019, 3).

Throughout my years of service in the private sector, public office, and private life, I have observed many people considering their emotions and feelings to be more critical than evidence-based facts. I think feelings and emotions have existed in humanity since time immemorial and have become part of it. As academia, we need to base our arguments and communication on evidence-based facts instead of personal emotions and feelings to justify our persuasion to our readers. The current coursepack clearly states the need to research facts based on evidence as “an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2019, 1). The evidence researched becomes a basis for developing a thesis more objectively after gaining enough knowledge (EUCLID 2019, 2). The more facts researched about a piece of evidence, the stronger one’s viewpoints will be.

3) **PLAGIARISM**

In the second chapter of this coursepack, EUCLID clearly stated plagiarism to be “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of the information” (EUCLID 2019, 5). In my earlier education in elementary and high school, there was no teaching about plagiarism. It was customary to be provided with textbooks or reading materials and use them to write assignments without citing the source of information. During my university undergraduate program, I got introduced to plagiarism and referenced the source of information used. As a teaching assistant at university, I experienced difficulty detecting plagiarism, especially in open free practical assignments, due to lack of evidence of plagiarism by the students even if there was suspicion of them having gotten help from fellow students. As government workers, we have practiced copying, re-using, and sharing some information within our departments, directorates, and the entire ministry without citing the source or author since the Ministry policy allows sharing data within the ministry.

While I understood that having someone write your paper and submitting as wrong and unethical, I have learned from this coursepack that it is plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5). Guided by the meaning of plagiarism, it becomes apparent to revise our copying and re-use information in organizations and government without citing to be compliant. I have

learned from working in government that all data generated by each unit belongs to the ministry, department, or agency and not the individual who developed the information. EUCLID encourages citing the author or source of the information you provide to avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 6).

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

Chapter six of the coursepack describes the American and British English variants of the World English (EUCLID 2019, 27), which are more similar than different. However, the coursepack provides the difference between the two variants, which include differences in pronunciations but with similar spelling, different spelling but the same pronunciation, same terms with different meaning but similar spelling and pronunciation (EUCLID 2019, 27-28). Before I read this coursepack, I did not clearly understand the difference between American and British English. Moreover, in my daily use of computer programs like Microsoft Word, the spelling checker would often try to correct words such as color, which did not make a lot of meaning; hence, I could use them interchangeably. It has become more apparent that one chooses to use either American or British English writing for consistency.

I have witnessed the date of birth on academic documents and official documents of close family members and friends being wrongly printed by interchanging the month with a day. Accordingly, this is partly due to the lack of specifying the date formats while filing documents. National academic papers issued by National Examinations Board are challenging to modify one's date of birth once printed, and the only option is to have an affidavit. EUCLID has in this coursepack provided different date formats (EUCLID 2019, 35). Therefore, every organization needs to adopt a specific data format for dates and make it more straightforward for accurate communication.

5) CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE

In chapter eight (8) of this coursepack, EUCLID describes the Chicago Style as “the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) and Kate Turabian’s Manual for Writers of Term Papers.” Furthermore, EUCLID states that the Turabian style is a simplified Chicago style applied to research papers (EUCLID 2019, 44). I have learned by reading this coursepack that abbreviations such as, i.e., e.g., must be in parenthetical comments injected in to text which I did not understand previously.

The three forms of capitalization discussed are of added knowledge to my earlier understanding about capitalization. Firstly the full caps, which requires capitalizing every character of a word used primarily on headings (EUCLID 2019, 45); I was instructed about the previous requirement right from elementary school. Secondly, the heading caps require to “capitalize the first and last words including all nouns, pronouns, adjectives, subordinating conjunctions and the first character after a colon in a title or heading”

(EUCLID 2019, 45). Previously I did not know of the need to capitalize the first character after a colon in a title and a heading. Thirdly, the sentence caps require capitalizing the first word of a title or header (EUCLID 2019, 45), which I was well aware of before.

The use of italics in a document confused me previously, and reading this coursepack has enlightened me on its proper use. Accordingly, during my years of being an instructor at a university, I would give computer students instructions to make words in italics for computer lesson assignments or exams without considering the proper use. This coursepack has enlightened my understanding of the appropriate use of italics. More specifically, I have learned in this coursepack that italics are used to emphasize a keyword or phrase and should be not be applied the next time the same word or phrase appears in the same work.

a) *Quotation Marks*

Besides my regular use of the quotation marks for quotes, I have learned from this EUCLID coursepack that the quotation marks can as well be used around a word or phrase given in a unique sense or purposefully misused and to enclose a translation of a non-English word (EUCLID 2019, 47). I have realized from reading the material provided by EUCLID about the permitted changes while using quotations. Firstly, the allowed changes include using brackets with a quote to emphasize the added words. Secondly, “italics are used within a quotation to add emphasis to words or phrases” (EUCLID 2019, 48); this is new to me as I did not know it previously. Thirdly, while quoting a foreign language, the requirement to reproduce all the accents and other marks as they appear in the original ((EUCLID 2019, 48) appears challenging as accents and characters of different languages may not be easy to reproduce. Lastly, I have learned that you can ignore a citation if you quote material that contains a quotation of another author (EUCLID 2019, 48).

b) *Chicago Page Formats*

The Chicago Manual of Style focuses on book publishing. It proposes some instructions while writing papers, and the Turabian Manual for writers is the official guide of applying the Chicago Style when writing term papers and dissertations (EUCLID 2019, 49). The requirement to leave a margin of one inch on all four margins of a page was recommended at my previous schools and is consistent with the Turabian Style as presented by the EUCLID coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 49). I have used the font Times Roman for text for most of my academic work as it has been the recommended font by the various institutions of learning I previously attended. The font appears clearer to view and read.

6) CONCLUSION

The first period of ACA-401, which I have undertaken as an orientation to the journey to obtain a Master’s degree in Diplomacy and International Affairs (MDIA), has been challenging. However, with continuous engagement with coursepack materials and

support from the EUCLID team, most specifically my instructor Dr. Kabiru Gulma, I have managed to comprehend and appreciate the study materials for the coursepack.

This coursepack has helped improve my understanding of English. It will continue to help me write professional work by first researching to get facts about a piece of evidence to come up with conclusions. The materials studied will help me avoid plagiarism, make good use of capitalization, cite the source of the work correctly using the required styles.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central Africa Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.